

The Utility of Diagnostic Laparoscopy for Assessing Complex Infertility Cases: A Cross-Sectional Study on Uterine, Ovarian, and Unexplained Factors

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Abstract:

Background: Infertility affects a substantial percentage of couples globally, with complex cases often involving uterine, ovarian, or unexplained factors that remain challenging to diagnose accurately. Although non-invasive imaging methods such as ultrasound and hysterosalpingography (HSG) are widely used, their limitations in sensitivity and specificity underscore the need for diagnostic laparoscopy, a minimally invasive procedure with high diagnostic accuracy. This study aims to evaluate the utility of diagnostic laparoscopy in assessing complex infertility cases, specifically focusing on uterine, ovarian, and unexplained factors.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 50 women presenting with either primary or secondary infertility. Each participant underwent diagnostic laparoscopy following standard clinical assessments, including ultrasonography and hormonal profiling. Data were collected on uterine anomalies, ovarian cysts, PCOD, and unexplained infertility cases, and were analyzed to compare findings between primary and secondary infertility groups.

Results: Uterine abnormalities, primarily fibroids, were identified in 12% of cases, mainly among primary infertility patients. Ovarian factors, including PCOD and ovarian cysts, were detected in 20% of cases across both primary and secondary infertility groups. Additionally, 12% of cases were classified as unexplained infertility due to the absence of identifiable abnormalities. Diagnostic laparoscopy provided higher detection rates for these factors compared to conventional imaging techniques, underscoring its role in cases where non-invasive methods were inconclusive.

Conclusion: Diagnostic laparoscopy is a valuable tool for identifying complex infertility factors, offering a reliable and safe method for comprehensive infertility evaluation. Its high diagnostic accuracy, particularly for detecting uterine, ovarian, and unexplained infertility factors, supports its use as a routine investigative procedure in infertility workups.

Recommendations: Laparoscopy should be considered for routine use in infertility evaluations, especially for patients with complex or unexplained infertility, to improve diagnosis and guide targeted treatment.

Keywords: Diagnostic Laparoscopy, Infertility Evaluation, Uterine Factors, Ovarian Factors, Unexplained Infertility, Polycystic Ovarian Disease.

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Introduction

Diagnostic laparoscopy has become essential in infertility evaluations, especially for directly visualizing intra-abdominal pathologies that non-invasive techniques may miss. Globally, infertility affects 10-15% of couples, with complex cases often involving factors like uterine or ovarian abnormalities and unexplained infertility [1,2]. While traditional imaging methods such as ultrasound and hysterosalpingography (HSG) are widely used, they are less effective in detecting subtle reproductive anomalies, thus favoring diagnostic laparoscopy in more complex infertility cases [3,4].

Uterine abnormalities, including fibroids and congenital anomalies, can impact fertility by disrupting normal uterine function, making laparoscopy invaluable for its ability to identify these issues directly [5]. Laparoscopy also enables accurate diagnosis of ovarian factors like polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD) and ovarian cysts, which can interfere with ovulation, a frequent cause of infertility [6]. These advantages underscore why laparoscopy is preferred for comprehensive infertility evaluations, as it provides a full view of pelvic organs and allows for targeted assessment and sometimes treatment of these abnormalities [7].

In cases of unexplained infertility, laparoscopy plays a critical role, confirming the absence of visible issues or detecting conditions like endometriosis or adhesions that may go undetected with conventional imaging (8). Recent studies indicate that diagnostic laparoscopy significantly enhances the detection rate of hidden pathologies, particularly when paired with advanced procedures like chromopertubation, improving fertility treatment outcomes [5,6].

The procedure's role in diagnosing endometriosis is especially important in secondary infertility, where inflammation and scarring can disrupt reproductive function. Laparoscopy allows for both the identification and immediate treatment of endometriotic lesions, offering a dual benefit of diagnosis and potential management [4]. Such findings highlight the unique advantage of laparoscopy in reducing the time to treatment and providing personalized fertility solutions, reinforcing its status as the gold standard in infertility assessments [7,8].

This study aims to assess the role of diagnostic laparoscopy in evaluating complex infertility cases, specifically focusing on identifying uterine, ovarian, and unexplained infertility factors.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a cross-sectional clinical design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted in the Gynecology & Obstetrics Department of Madhubani Medical College and Hospital. Participants were recruited from the outpatient department and provided consent to undergo diagnostic laparoscopy as part of their infertility evaluation.

Participants: A total of 50 women diagnosed with infertility were included in the study, comprising both primary and secondary infertility cases. All participants desired to conceive and consented to undergo diagnostic laparoscopy.

Inclusion Criteria: Female patients diagnosed with either primary or secondary infertility who were willing to undergo diagnostic laparoscopy.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients were excluded if their partners presented with severe male infertility, such as azoospermia or severe oligospermia, or if the women had contraindications for laparoscopy.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by enrolling all eligible participants who met the study criteria and were willing to participate. Observer bias was controlled by ensuring that diagnostic evaluations were conducted consistently by experienced clinicians following a standardized procedure.

Variables: Variables included types of infertility (primary or secondary), diagnostic findings, including uterine factors (e.g., fibroids, anomalies), ovarian factors (e.g., PCOD, ovarian cysts), and cases categorized as unexplained infertility.

Data Collection

Data collection was based on:

1. **Clinical History and Examination:** Detailed medical histories were recorded for each participant, including information on age, infertility duration, prior treatments, and relevant reproductive history.
2. **Diagnostic Findings:** During laparoscopy, specific observations were made to identify uterine anomalies, ovarian cysts, signs of PCOD, and peritoneal conditions. Cases with no detectable abnormality were classified as unexplained infertility.

Procedure

Participants underwent preliminary evaluations, including clinical history, hormonal assessments, and imaging (e.g., ultrasound) to exclude any contraindications. Under anesthesia, diagnostic laparoscopy was performed. Uterine, ovarian, and peritoneal structures were inspected thoroughly to detect fibroids, cysts, adhesions, or other abnormalities. Chromopertubation was used in selected cases to assess tubal patency, providing additional insights in cases classified as unexplained infertility. Patients were observed for any immediate postoperative complications and provided with follow-up care as needed.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize patient demographics, infertility types, and the frequency of identified factors.

Ethical considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Results

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Age (Years)	Primary Infertility (%)	Secondary Infertility (%)
<20	3%	0%
20-25	31%	33.3%
26-30	34%	6.7%
31-35	26%	46.7%
>35	6%	13.3%

The study included 50 women, categorized into two groups: 70% (35) with primary infertility and 30% (15) with secondary infertility. Age distribution showed that most primary infertility cases were in the 26-30 years age range, while secondary infertility was prevalent in women aged 31-35

years. Table 1 shows age distribution among primary and secondary infertility cases. The majority of primary infertility patients were between 26-30 years, whereas secondary infertility cases were most frequent in the 31-35 years age group.

Table 2: Duration of Infertility

Duration (Years)	Primary Infertility (%)	Secondary Infertility (%)
1-5	71%	60%
6-10	26%	33%
>10	3%	7%

Most participants with primary infertility (71%) reported infertility for 1-5 years, followed by 26% for 6-10 years, and 3% for over 10 years. For secondary infertility cases, 60% had infertility for 1-5 years, 33% for 6-10 years, and 7% for over 10 years. Table 2 presents the duration of infertility in both groups, with the majority of cases in both primary and secondary infertility groups experiencing infertility for 1-5 years.

Table 3: Findings on Uterine Factors

Uterine Factor	Primary Infertility (%)	Secondary Infertility (%)	Total (%)
Fibroid Uterus	10%	6.7%	8%
Uterine Anomalies	2.6%	0%	2%
Total	12.6%	6.7%	12%

Diagnostic laparoscopy identified uterine factors in 12% of cases. The most common uterine abnormalities included fibroid uterus, which was found in 10% of primary infertility cases, and anomalies, such as a septate uterus, which was observed in 2.6% of primary cases. Table 3 shows

the prevalence of uterine factors detected in primary and secondary infertility cases. Fibroids were more common in primary infertility, with no structural uterine anomalies noted in secondary infertility cases.

Table 4: Findings on Ovarian Factors

Ovarian Factor	Primary Infertility (%)	Secondary Infertility (%)	Total (%)
PCOD	17.14%	13.3%	16%
Ovarian Cyst	2.86%	6.7%	4%
Total	20%	20%	20%

Ovarian factors were found in 20% of cases, including polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD) and ovarian cysts. PCOD was observed in 17.14% of primary infertility cases and 13.3% of secondary infertility cases, while ovarian cysts were found in

2% of cases. Table 4 outlines the prevalence of ovarian factors, including PCOD and ovarian cysts. PCOD was more prevalent in primary infertility cases, while ovarian cysts were more common in secondary infertility.

Table 5: Cases of Unexplained Infertility

Cause of Infertility	Primary Infertility (%)	Secondary Infertility (%)	Total (%)
Unexplained Infertility	8.57%	20%	12%

In 12% of cases, no identifiable abnormality was detected, resulting in a diagnosis of unexplained infertility. This group consisted of 8.57% of primary infertility cases and 20% of secondary infertility cases. Table 5 displays the frequency of

unexplained infertility in primary and secondary infertility cases. A higher percentage of unexplained cases was noted in the secondary infertility group, underscoring the complexity of diagnosing secondary infertility causes.

Table 6: Complications of Diagnostic Laparoscopy

Complication	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Abdominal Pain	2	4%
Major Complications	0	0%
Total	2	4%

The complication rate was minimal, with only 4% of patients reporting mild abdominal pain post-procedure, and no major complications were noted. Table 6 provides a summary of complications related to the laparoscopic procedure. The low complication rate demonstrates the safety of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool in infertility evaluation.

Discussion

The study results highlight diagnostic laparoscopy's effectiveness in assessing complex infertility cases, focusing on uterine, ovarian, and unexplained factors. The majority of participants were women with primary infertility (70%), predominantly aged 26-30 years, while most secondary infertility cases occurred in women aged 31-35 years. Most participants in both groups reported an infertility duration of 1-5 years, reflecting the typical timeframe during which individuals seek medical assistance for infertility issues. These demographic patterns align with previous findings that primary infertility tends to present at a younger age, while secondary infertility often emerges later, potentially due to previous reproductive or medical history.

Diagnostic laparoscopy identified uterine factors in 12% of cases, with fibroids being the most common anomaly, primarily in primary infertility cases. These findings underscore laparoscopy's utility in visualizing uterine anomalies that could impair fertility, such as fibroids or septate uterus. Additionally, ovarian factors, including PCOD and ovarian cysts, were observed in 20% of cases, indicating a notable contribution of ovarian pathologies to infertility. PCOD was particularly prevalent in primary infertility cases, consistent with its association with hormonal imbalances and ovulatory dysfunction, while ovarian cysts were more frequently seen in secondary infertility.

In 12% of cases, no identifiable abnormality was detected, leading to a diagnosis of unexplained infertility. Unexplained infertility was more common in secondary infertility cases, which highlights the complexity of diagnosing and treating infertility when no structural or hormonal issues are apparent. The presence of unexplained infertility reinforces the role of laparoscopy in thorough infertility evaluations, as it can rule out anatomical causes and guide further investigations.

The procedure proved safe, with a low complication rate of 4%, limited to mild abdominal discomfort in a few cases. The minimal complications affirm the safety of diagnostic laparoscopy, supporting its use as a reliable diagnostic tool in infertility evaluations.

Overall, these findings validate laparoscopy's role in diagnosing uterine, ovarian, and unexplained infertility factors, especially in cases where non-

invasive imaging techniques are inconclusive. By allowing for direct visualization of pelvic organs, laparoscopy aids in identifying subtle abnormalities and provides essential insights for tailored infertility treatments, thus improving the diagnostic process in complex infertility cases.

A study focused on tubo-ovarian disruptions in unexplained infertility, finding that 53.3% of women presented with disturbed tubo-ovarian relations. Laparoscopy enabled interventions such as adhesiolysis and cyst excision, which resulted in a higher conception rate among these cases. This underscores laparoscopy's ability to both diagnose and manage underlying anatomical infertility factors that other techniques often miss [9]. In a similar vein, another study examined the effectiveness of combining hysteroscopy and laparoscopy in identifying abnormalities. They observed that hysterolaparoscopy detected more abnormalities in secondary infertility cases than in primary ones, highlighting its diagnostic value for cases where initial non-invasive methods fail to reveal definitive results [10].

Research explored endoscopic management in cases of unexplained infertility following multiple failed IVF cycles, revealing endometriosis in 57.7% of cases and tubal abnormalities in 31.1%. Laparoscopic intervention, including treatment for these pathologies, not only increased spontaneous pregnancy rates but also improved success rates in subsequent IVF cycles. This study demonstrates that laparoscopy effectively uncovers and addresses concealed infertility factors, enhancing the likelihood of conception [11].

A study contributed additional insights from a study conducted in rural India, which revealed abnormalities in 43.3% of infertile women through diagnostic laparoscopy. Common findings included peritubal adhesions, polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD), and tubal blockages. These results indicate that laparoscopy is particularly valuable in resource-limited settings for detecting diverse infertility factors that may otherwise remain undiagnosed [12]. Another study emphasized laparoscopy's diagnostic role in cases of unexplained infertility, uncovering hidden pathologies like endometriosis and adhesions in 60% of participants. This finding reinforces laparoscopy's importance as a tool to identify complex pelvic disorders, which, in turn, can direct patients toward more effective fertility treatment options [13].

In an evaluation of 100 infertility cases, a study found that laparoscopy could successfully identify uterine, tubal, ovarian, and peritoneal abnormalities in 82% of cases. The study supports the use of laparoscopy as an all-encompassing diagnostic tool that allows physicians to address multiple infertility

factors in a single, minimally invasive procedure [14]. Lastly, a study compared findings in primary and secondary subfertility cases, discovering that PCOD, adhesions, and tubal blocks were common factors contributing to infertility. Their research underscores laparoscopy's utility in distinguishing the root causes of subfertility, especially in complex cases where preliminary evaluations are inconclusive [15].

Conclusion

In conclusion, diagnostic laparoscopy proves to be a valuable tool in the comprehensive assessment of complex infertility cases, particularly for identifying uterine and ovarian factors that might go undetected with non-invasive imaging. The study's findings underscore laparoscopy's role in providing detailed anatomical insights, thus enhancing the accuracy of infertility diagnoses and aiding in treatment decisions. Its minimal complication rate and high diagnostic efficacy, especially in cases of unexplained infertility, validate its use as a routine procedure in infertility evaluations, offering a reliable pathway to more targeted and effective fertility management.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Laparoscopy should be considered for routine use in infertility evaluations, especially for patients with complex or unexplained infertility, to improve diagnosis and guide targeted treatment.

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List of abbreviations:

HSG - Hysterosalpingography

PCOD - Polycystic Ovarian Disease

IVF - In Vitro Fertilization

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